

EFFECT OF YARN CROSS-SECTIONAL SHAPES AND CRIMP ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF 3D WOVEN COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

This paper describes the effect of yarn cross-sectional shape and crimp in the weft yarns on the mechanical properties of carbon/epoxy 3D woven composites. Their effects on the stiffness, static strength and fatigue strength are studied by using finite element analysis of unit cell models and applying numerical homogenisation techniques.

Keywords: 3D woven composites, numerical homogenisation technique, damage modelling, fatigue strength modelling

1. Introduction

Complex internal geometries of yarns in three dimensional woven textile composites affect their mechanical properties such as stiffness and strength. Their effects can be studied either experimentally or numerically. Lomov et al. [1] presented a sequence of steps required for finite element based numerical study of woven textile composites by using a unit cell approach. Scope of this approach were prediction of stiffness and strength properties, damage initiation and damage propagation modelling. Callus et al. [2] studied tensile properties and damage mechanism of 3D glass reinforced polymer composites with 3D orthogonal, normal layered interlock and offset layered interlock weave under tensile loading. They observed similar failure mechanisms for these weave architectures and reduction by 20 - 30% in their elastic modulus. Kuo et al. [3] studied the failure characteristics of 3D woven composites under transverse shear. They undertook shear testing of three types of 3D woven composites made with identical internal yarn structures but with different external loop patterns. Their study shows matrix cracking and yarn debonding appears first in all specimens. Tan et al. [4,5] studied the behaviour of 3D orthogonal woven composites using experimental techniques and finite element analysis based on laminate theory. They studied the damage behaviour of those composites under tensile loading along the weft and the warp directions. They observed good agreement for stiffness predictions whereas difference in failure strength predictions was significant mainly due to assumptions made in the study. The literature available on the variation in strength and fatigue properties of 3D woven composites with different yarn shape and their effects on the mechanical properties are not reported so far.

In this article, parametric studies are undertaken to investigate the effects of yarn shape and crimp on stiffness, static strength and fatigue strength properties of 3D woven composites. In section 2, the geometry of the 3D woven unit cells considered for the analysis are presented followed by approaches for modelling damage under quasi-static and fatigue loads in section 3. Section 4 describes a parametric study of the effect of yarn shape and crimp on the mechanical behaviour of 3D woven composites. Section 5 draws conclusions from the results of the analysis.

Model A

Model B

Model C

Model D

Model E

Fig. 1: Unit cell models of 3D woven composites with different weft yarn shapes.

2. Numerical Modelling of the 3D woven unit cells

In this study, steps proposed by Lomov et al. [1] are used. First, mechanical and fatigue properties of yarns were predicted by developing micro level model. At this level, hexagonal unit cell with aligned fibres is considered. At next stage, unit cell models at meso level with selected weft cross sections were developed. SOLID92 (10 node tetrahedral) elements were used in finite element analysis using a commercial finite element package, ANSYS 11 at both levels. Local fibre orientations in the yarns at meso level are assigned using local coordinate systems.

In order to investigate the effects of yarn shape on the mechanical behaviour of 3D woven composites, five unit cell models of 3D woven composites with different weft yarn shapes were constructed and shown in Fig. 1. The cross-sectional shape of binder and warp yarns and their fibre volume fractions are same in all unit cell models. The fraction of the total volume of fibres contribution by the weft yarns are also the same. The fibre volume fraction in yarns is assumed to be 70%. The global fibre volume fraction contribution from the weft, warp and binder yarns are 15.76%, 10.5% and 3.93% respectively. The overall fibre volume fraction of the unit cell is 30.19%.

In order to study the effects of crimp, two types of unit cells having different weft yarn, shown in Fig. 2, were modelled. One has crimp in the weft yarns at the regions of binder yarn crossover points and other has straight weft yarns. The shapes and fibre volume fractions of binder and warp yarns are same in both unit cell models.

Fig. 2: Unit cell models of 3D woven composites with crimped and non-crimped weft yarns

3. Modelling of damage under quasi-static and fatigue loads

A maximum stress criterion is used to model initiation of damage in the yarns. At micro scale level, the material stiffness and strength properties of fibre and resin are used to calculate the stiffness and strength properties of yarns. At this level, the failure strengths of the yarns under different loadings are obtained. Further, these properties are used in the meso scale level simulations. At meso level, quasi-static tensile loads in different directions were applied to calculate the failure strengths and stress-strain

behaviour of 3D woven composites. When the maximum stress in either yarns or the resin is greater than or equal to the corresponding yarn or resin failure strength, failure initiation occurs in that constituent. After failure initiation, a stiffness degradation approach is applied. The fatigue damage simulations are also based on the maximum stress criterion at micro and meso scales, and use the maximum stress versus number of cycles (S-N) data of resin and the fibre. Using the S-N data and stiffness properties of the resin and fibre, the maximum stress vs. number of cycles data of the yarns are obtained in transverse and longitudinal directions. These are used as the S-N data of the yarns in the meso scale unit cell model to initiate fatigue damage. Then, again by applying cyclic loading along the normal directions of the meso scale unit cell model, the maximum stress vs. number of cycles are obtained for the 3D woven composites. This procedure is described in detail by Kari et al.[7].

4. Results and discussion

In this analysis, the 3D woven composite is comprised of carbon fibres and epoxy resin. Their mechanical properties and corresponding S-N data are given in Tables 1 and 3 respectively [6]. S-N data of the resin and fibre were retrieved from experimental fatigue tests of uni-directional fibre composites [6]. It is observed that the resin exhibits elastic-plastic behaviour. In order to simplify the present analysis, only elastic behaviour of the resin and fibre is assumed. The mechanical properties of yarns are calculated using the numerical homogenisation technique at micro scale and are shown in Table 2. In Table 2, the comparison between the FE results and analytical predictions by Huang [6] for the stiffness properties of fibre bundles (uni-directional composites). The S-N data obtained for fibre bundles using micro scale analysis are shown in Table 4. Results related to warp, weft and through-thickness directions are represented by 1, 2 and 3 respectively in this section.

4.1 Effect of yarn shape on the mechanical behaviour

4.1.1 Stiffness predictions

The stiffness predictions for all five models are given in Table 5. From Table 5, it can be observed that variation in their stiffness values are minor as stiffness properties depend mainly on the amount of fibres in that directions.

Table 1: Mechanical properties of carbon fibres and epoxy resin

	E_{11} (GPa)	$E_{22}=E_{33}$ (GPa)	$\nu_{21} = \nu_{31}$	ν_{23}	$G_{21} = G_{31}$ (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	Failure strength (MPa)
Fibre	194.3	15.4	0.275	0.275	18.1	18.1	1880
Resin	3.45	3.45	0.35	0.35	1.28	1.28	26.4

Table 2: Stiffness predictions of uni-directional composites.

Volume fraction (70%)	E_{11} (GPa)	$E_{22}=E_{33}$ (GPa)	$\nu_{21} = \nu_{31}$	ν_{23}	$G_{21} = G_{31}$ (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	σ_{11} (MPa)	σ_{22} (MPa)
FE results	139	9.26	0.287	0.25	5.23	5.65	1354	20.4

Analytical results [6]	137	9.6	0.298		5.24		1323	38.5
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Table 3: Constituent fatigue properties of carbon and epoxy at R=0.1 and $\omega = 18$ Hz

	Cycle Number (N)			
	10^3	10^4	10^5	10^6
σ_u^{Nf} (MPa) (fibre)	1880	1780	1683	1586
σ_u^{Nm} (MPa) (resin)	26.4	24.8	23.2	21.8

Table 4: S-N data of the yarns in longitudinal and transverse directions.

Cycle Number	10^3	10^4	10^5	10^6
Longitudinal strength (MPa)	1354	1289	1205	1124
Transverse strength (MPa)	20.4	18.09	16.13	14.2

Table 5: Stiffness properties of 3D woven composites with different weft yarn shapes

	Model A	Model B	Model C	Model D	Model E
E_{11} (GPa)	31.80	31.78	31.83	31.83	31.79
E_{22} (GPa)	45.97	45.81	45.70	45.47	45.60
E_{33} (GPa)	7.18	7.03	6.99	7.02	7.01
G_{13} (GPa)	2.14	2.13	2.13	2.14	2.13
G_{23} (GPa)	2.12	2.07	2.09	2.11	2.07
G_{12} (GPa)	2.65	2.70	2.67	2.62	2.68

4.1.2 Static strength predictions

First, initial failure strengths are calculated for the unit cell models, where failure occurs in the resin rich pockets or in the yarns subjected to transverse loading. Table 6 shows the initial failure strengths of 3D woven composites in weft, warp and through thickness directions. It can be observed that with changes in the yarn shape in weft direction, the initial failure strength in the warp direction varies. In model A, initial failure occurs due to resin failure in the weft yarns at a stress of 23.71 MPa, which is the lowest among all the unit cells models. This is due to the higher stress concentration in this model with sharp edges of the weft yarns. The highest initial failure strength of 30.92 MPa is observed for model E where failure occurs in the resin rich regions. In model E, the weft yarn edges are semi-circular in shape resulting in reduced stress concentrations. Initial failure strengths in longitudinal direction vary by up to 30 % for different models. This variation is believed to be due to the presence of sharp edges in some of the cross sections leading to stress concentrations. A similar trend can be observed in the through thickness direction where the variation is up to 15%.

In the weft direction, A and C have the largest initial failure strengths among all models. Hence, results of these two models are further analysed. Comparisons of stress vs. strain curves of these models in the warp and the weft directions are shown in Figs. 3 and 4 respectively. When tensile loading is applied in the warp direction, final failure occurs at 190.68 MPa and 190.57 MPa in Model A and C respectively

after failure initiation in the warp yarns. In models A and C, the warp yarns have the same shape and fibre volume fraction causing negligible difference in their final failure strengths. When tensile loading is applied in the weft direction, final failure occurs due to failure of the weft yarns at a stress of 238.47 MPa and 265.36 MPa in models A and C respectively. This difference in final failure strength in the weft direction is because of stress concentration effects due to sharp weft yarn edges in model A.

4.1.3 Fatigue strength predictions

Fatigue strength of model A and C is calculated by applying cyclic loads in their weft

Table 6: Initial failure strengths of 3D woven composites with different weft yarn shapes.

Models	Warp direction		Through-Thickness direction		Weft direction	
	Strength (MPa)	Failure mode	Strength (MPa)	Failure mode	Strength (MPa)	Failure mode
Model A	23.71	Yarn	8.21	Yarn	48.25	Yarn
Model B	29.15	Resin & Yarn	7.98	Yarn	44.58	Resin
Model C	29.17	Resin	7.08	Yarn	47.74	Yarn
Model D	27.30	Resin & Yarn	7.15	Yarn	47.72	Yarn
Model E	30.92	Resin	7.95	Yarn	47.51	Yarn

and warp directions. When the cyclic load is applied along the warp direction, the weft yarns and a portion of the binder yarns are subjected to transverse loading causing the failure of these yarns due to resin failure. Figs. 5 and 6 show comparisons of their initial and final fatigue failure strengths. From Fig. 5, it can be observed that the initial fatigue failure strength of model C is slightly higher than that of model A. This is due to the fact that model C has weft yarns with rectangular shape whereas

Fig. 3: Stress strain behaviour of model A and C under quasi-static tensile loading in the warp direction.

model A has sharper edges, leading to higher stress concentrations as discussed above. From Fig. 6, it can be observed that the final fatigue failure strengths of model A and C are almost same. In this case, the final failure strength represents failure initiation in the warp yarns and in model A and C, the warp yarns have the same shape and mechanical properties, so the final fatigue failure strength is the same.

Fig. 4: Stress strain behaviour of model A and C under quasi-static tensile loading in the weft direction

Fig. 5: Initial fatigue failure strengths of models A and C in the warp direction.

Fig. 6: Final fatigue failure strengths of Models A and C in the warp direction.

Fig. 7 shows final fatigue failure strengths of models A and C in the weft direction. It can be observed that the failure strength of model C are higher than those of model A. In this case, the final fatigue strength represents failure initiation in the weft yarns due to fibre failure. Because of higher stress concentrations in the weft yarns of model A compared to model C, the final fatigue failure strengths of model A is less than that of model C.

Fig. 7: Final fatigue failure strengths of Models A and C in weft direction.

4.2 Effect of crimp on the mechanical behaviour of 3D woven composites

Here, the overall fibre volume fraction in carbon and epoxy is as follows: in weft direction: 17.06%, in warp direction: 10.28%, in binder yarns: 1.35%, the resin volume fraction: 71.31%. The effects of crimp on the stiffness and static strength properties are investigated with and without crimp in the weft yarns. In the crimped and the non-crimped unit cells, the warp and binder yarns have the same shape and stiffness properties. The material properties of the resin are taken from Table 1. The

stiffness properties of yarns are taken from Table 2. The calculated failure strengths of yarns are given in Table 2.

4.2.1 Stiffness properties

The stiffness properties of 3D woven composites are obtained using numerical homogenisation techniques for both crimped and non-crimp composites and given in Table 9. The Young's modulus in the weft direction (E_{22}) for the crimped composite is 10.12% lower than the non-crimp composite. For other stiffness properties, the differences are under 1.5%.

Table 9: Stiffness properties of crimped and non-crimp composite.

3D woven composites	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	E_{33} (GPa)	G_{13} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)
With crimp	30.62	42.52	6.28	2.02	2.04	2.5
Without crimp	30.48	47.31	6.31	2.01	2.01	2.51
% difference	0.4	10.12	0.4	0.4	1.49	0.4

4.2.2 Static strength predictions

Quasi-static tensile loading was applied in the weft direction to calculate stress vs. strain behaviour of crimped and non-crimp 3D woven composites and shown in Fig. 8. The final failure strength of crimped composites are approximately 50% lower than the non-crimp composites. This is due to higher stress concentrations at the crimped regions, which cause fibre failure at low strain level. Final failure represents fibre failure initiation in the weft yarns.

Fig. 8: Comparison of stress vs. strain curves for the crimped and non-crimp 3D woven composites.

5. Conclusions

The effects of yarn shape and crimp in the weft yarns of carbon/epoxy 3D woven composites are analysed using finite element analysis of unit cell models at the meso scale. It is observed that if the yarn shape has sharp edges the initial and final failure strengths are lower than those of the yarns having smooth edges. It is further observed

that the failure strengths decrease with crimp in the weft yarns due to high stress concentrations in the crimped regions.

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